
Review

Influence of Consumer Awareness and Buying Behavior on Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM). A Study of Nestle.

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Abstract: Sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) is increasingly becoming a strategic imperative for organizations aiming at reconciling profit maximization and environmental as well social responsibilities. The current study aims to understand the purchase intention of the customers and then affects such awareness through practices regarding sustainable supply chain management by Nestle, a reputed company in FMCG (Food & Beverages). Consumer awareness campaigns related to environmental and ethical issues are already making the likes of Nestle require adhering to sustainable sourcing, production and distribution processes (Ahi & Searcy, 2013). The research takes a case study strategy that incorporates qualitative and quantitative records from patron surveys, interviews with Nestle executives, and agency reports to examine how customer expectancies tell you about forwards Chain necessities of Nestle. The sustainable consumer trend has led Nestle to rely more on responsible supply chain management, including in raw materials sourcing, packaging and waste reduction efforts (Nestle 2023). In the face of growing demand for transparency and ethical sourcing from consumers, Nestle has stepped up sustainability efforts such as zero-waste factories in key markets around the world; industry-redefining supplying chain safeguards to protect cocoa drinkers from child labor via partnerships like its supply partnership with Swiss forensic laboratory Merieux NutriSciences which strengthens engagement along standards set out by Free The Children's Cocoa Action program; or how they will manage precious fresh water resources responsibly addressing concerns that come towards them demanding it be done differently due policies all because everyone embraces these positives trends under this broader umbrella opportunity situation we see today. Consumer buying behavior additionally has been further leaning toward products that pleasing them like mindful purchasing and this too become a strong driver for Nestle to include sustainability in their supply chain operations (Vermeir & Verbeke, 2006). The research reinforces the fact that consumer awareness and buying behavior are key drivers (Conclude). It stresses on why companies need to react quickly because of social as well environmental issues. The case of Nestle exemplifies a way to move beyond consumer expectations and employ sustainability as the support for global competencies in business practice (Bocken et al. 2014). New research is needed to delve into the downstream financial and operational effects of these evolving consumer appetites on corporate sustainability strategies over time.

Keywords: Sustainable Supply Chain Management, Consumer Awareness, Buying Behavior, Nestle, Sustainability, Ethical Sourcing.

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Introduction

Sustainability has emerged as a critical issue in global supply chains, propelled by heightened consumer awareness and a transition towards ecologically responsible operations. Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM) denotes the incorporation of environmentally, socially, and economically sustainable principles into supply chain operations, guaranteeing enduring viability and ethical conduct (Ahi & Searcy, 2013). As consumer knowledge of environmental and social issues increases, corporations are obligated to implement sustainable practices to meet customer expectations and continue competitiveness. Consumer behavior, which includes decision-making processes affected by attitudes, preferences, and knowledge, is pivotal in influencing sustainable behaviors (Chen, 2020). Nestle, a leading global food and beverage corporation, serves as an exemplary case study for analyzing the impact of consumer awareness and purchasing behavior on sustainable supply chain management (SSCM). The company's vast worldwide supply chain and dedication to sustainability objectives, including attaining net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050, underscore the necessity of incorporating sustainability into its operations (Nestle, 2023). Increasing consumer apprehensions regarding health, environmental sustainability, and ethical sourcing directly impact Nestle's initiatives in sustainable procurement, waste minimization, and supplier management (Tencati et al., 2016). This study examines the influence of customer awareness and purchasing behavior on Nestle's sustainable supply chain management practices, offering insights into the relationship between market demand and organizational sustainability efforts. This research seeks to elucidate the relationship between consumer behavior and company sustainability, thereby promoting a circular economy and tackling global environmental issues.

Problem Statement

This paper provides a research proposition, which focuses on Sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) for companies trying to balance between economic growth and environmental-social responsibilities. Nonetheless, there is limited exploration of the impact consumer awareness and buying behavior has on these initiatives despite significant efforts by organizations in implementing sustainable practices. There is a growing understanding among businesses and practitioners that consumer demand for transparency, socially responsible practices (a.k.a. ethical sourcing), and environmental sustainability are emerging as sources of pressures to prompt evolution in supply chain management practice (Ahi & Searcy 2013). Sustainability in supply chains a strong example of this can be seen at Nestle, the world's largest food & beverage enterprise; one that ironically competes with Tesla for almost all customers' items. Supply chain management which closely aligns with sustainability goals from vendors and suppliers is an operational challenge but more so becoming a strategic exigency.

Consumers are becoming increasingly aware of the social and environmental implications of their purchases (Vermeir & Verbeke, 2006), leading to increased scrutiny from consumers that Nestle is struggling with. Consumers are more and more requesting this type of value as a means to meet their needs: fair trade, eco-packages, and understanding the local grower (Bocken et al., 2014). So, companies such as Nestle have no choice but to reevaluate their supply chain approaches, balancing changing customer and consumer expectations with functional efficiency-financial performance against operational expenditure. This undermines efforts to improve sustainability along the supply chain, by creating a barrier for firms supplying PDFs and SSCMs looking to address consumer behavior.

Even though Nestle has introduced initiatives, such as sustainable cocoa sourcing and zero-waste factories (Nestle 2023), to address these concerns there is still room for research on how consumer conscious involvement could influence SSCM within the company. This relationship is essential to both unlocking drivers behind successful sustainability strategies and enabling businesses to deliver against consumer expectations in the short term with long-term supply chain resilience.

Research Objective

The key purpose of this study is to explore impact analysis, customer awareness and consumer behavior on Nestle with regards sustainable supply chain management (SSCM) practices. In particular, the current research looks into how

rising consumer consciousness viz environmental and ethical concerns drive its sustainability initiatives in the corporate context *ceteris paribus* for worldwide supply chain. As customers increasingly demand greater transparency and responsibility from corporations: how much does such expectation lead to the sustainability actions of Nestlé for e.g. sustainable sourcing, waste minimization, responsible production (Ahi & Searcy 2013; Bocken et al.)

Additionally, it would like to comprehend why such shifts leave Nestle no other choice than managing sustainable packaging and raw material procurement strategies (Vermeir & Verbeke 2006). The aim of this paper is to learn from Nestle as a case study in driving for SSCM, thereby elucidating how multinational companies can employ consumer awareness that may lead sustainability into their supply chains (Nestle 2023) The paper, in turn, intends to provide empirical support for the relationship between consumer behavior and corporate sustainability initiatives as a significant contribution towards literature on SSCM.

Literature Review

Over the past few years, Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM) has become a hot research topic as firms are not only concerned with economic performance but also increasingly have to account for their social and environmental behavior. From the perspective of SSCM, a set of sustainable manufacturing practices can be integrated into all operations and processes related to supply chains like sourcing, production, processing, logistics & transportation, waste management and others with acknowledging their environmental and social implications (Ahi& Searcy 2013). According to Bocken et al. (2014) several studies have indicated that SSCM has become an increasingly important part of corporate social responsibility and long-term profitability. Consumer awareness and buying behavior: critical factors for sustainable supply chain management - a case study of Nestle.

Consumer awareness and sustainability

Over the last several decades there was a significant increase of environmental awareness amongst consumers that shifted corporate sustainability initiatives. Nowadays consumers are more aware of the environmental and social effects related to purchase decisions so there is an increasing trend in demand for sustainable products. (Vermeir and Verbeke 2006) found that environmentally and socially aware consumers are more likely to buy sustainable products. As consumers have grown increasingly aware of the environmental impact and social costs associated with fast-fashion, many companies are being pressured to adopt sustainability in their sourcing and supply chain activities or risk losing market share as image damage occurs.

Consumer awareness also, in the backdrop of SSCM is a dominant instrumentality that answerable firms be made to confine their practices (Pagell & Wu, 2009). Some companies such as Nestle have responded to these consumer issues by implementing sustainability measures equivalent to cocoa sourcing, responsible water management and zero waste initiatives (Nestle 2023). These measures are very often dictated by consumer demand for transparency and ethical conduct, as in food or beverage market cases where things like child labor, deforestation use of resources etc., come to surface.

Buying Behavior and Ethical Sourcing

On the other hand, corporate sustainability is greatly influenced by consumer buying behavior. Literature review Ethical consumption, defined as buying goods and products which are related to ethics such as sustaining the environment; human rights, fair trade that is gaining more importance in today's world (Bocken et al., 2014). One theory is that consumer demand for ethically-sourced goods drives firms to reorganize their resource- and production networks in accordance with these values Moreover, according to (Pagell & Wu 2009), ethical consumers are willing pay more for products made in a manner that is consistent with their moral and environmentalism values thereby furthering rewarding companies that have implemented environmentally conscious supply chain strategies.

Findings from several studies have revealed that consumer attitudes towards sustainable product sourcing and utilization of eco-friendly packaging are shaping Nestlé's operational choices (Vermeir & Verbeke, 2006). In consideration of increasing interest in environmentally friendly products, Nestle includes environmental sustainability as one of the core elements to its business by aiming at reducing greenhouse gas emissions, ensuring water stewardship and promoting responsible sourcing. In fact, the trend toward pro-social consumer choice has encouraged Nestle and other multinational giants to redesign their supply chain capabilities to accommodate consumers without jeopardizing bottom lines (Ahi & Searcy, 2013).

SSCM and Corporate Strategy

The move towards a sustainable supply chain is both about responding to external pressures from consumers as well as gaining competitive advantage. For companies SSCM ensures operational efficiency, waste minimization and cost saving opportunities but it also helps ensure a good reputation for the brand or product which results in higher customer loyalty (Bocken et al., 2014). With SSCM practices in place, market dynamics and associated risks concerning resource scarcity (environment), regulatory compliance issues are reduced thereby ensuring basic sustainability for long term survival.

As an example of Nestle's approach to embedding sustainability within all areas of its operation, the company is implementing zero-waste factories and seeking sustainable sources for raw materials such as cocoa and coffee (Nestle 2023). In this way, Nestle meets consumer needs and at the same time further cements its reputation on a global level as an ethical manufacturer. Such companies are expected to achieve more harmonizations with the challenges of international supply chains as well continue to be forced by all stakeholders exemplified above for sustainability demanding (Pagell & Wu, 2009).

Problems in the Execution of SSCM

Although it offers many advantages, at the same time companies do find it challenging to implement SSCM in their organization. For instance, costs to sustain resource sourcing can be high (which is what the purchasers are looking for), technology has its limitations and monitoring suppliers' sustainability standard compliance by firms in purchasing organizations is complex (Ahi & Searcy, 2013). Moreover, well-known is the gap between what consumers state they prefer and their actual purchasing behavior: the so-called "attitude-behavior gap" (Vermeir and Verbeke 2006). The need to bridge this gap is a key challenge for companies like Nestle, which has committed €120 million in an investment fund that looks promising on paper – but must also be able prove its sustainability investments create value for the company and are scalable.

Another challenge is to have full transparency in the supply chains, taking into account that we are dealing with suppliers globally and sometimes even from regions where sustainability standards might be not as strict. For instance, companies such as Nestlé have worked to increase transparency and traceability within their supply chains through technology that tracks where raw materials originate from so compliance with ethics can be ensured (Nestle, 2023). Bridging the information gap. Though many multinational companies are still on a journey to achieve complete transparency; it is proving far more difficult than that for some others.

Theoretical Perspective

The influence of two determinants, customer awareness and buying behavior on SSCM. This study has potential contributions to theoriesualitative theoretical framework employed as an explanatory tool toward the understanding of a relationship between consumer behavior, corporate sustainability strategies and supply chain management (Barney et al. These theories underpin the explanation for corporate sustainability initiatives and how consumer expectations, consumers themselves influence business. Community-Based Mobile Technologies support.

1. Stakeholder Theory

Stakeholder Theory is an important theoretical paradigm underpinning this study which posits that companies have to take into account the interests of all stakeholders other than shareholders in their decision-making. The theory implies the assignment of accountability not only to shareholders, but also customers, employees, suppliers and society (Freeman et al. 1984). Stakeholder theory explains how consumer interest in sustainability can lead companies such as Nestlé to become more responsible supply chains, through the lens of SSCM. Thus, as consumer concern for ethics and search for transparency in source rise (Mitchell, Agle & Wood 1997) companies find themselves pushed on to a tightrope of stakeholder pressures compounds encroach upon their legitimacy and market share.

A growing consumer interest in matters of the environment and social betterment (e.g. fair trade, ethical sourcing) makes consumers a key stakeholder for corporate sustainability outcomes. The stakeholder theory emphasizes that businesses, who do not take the interests of their customers into account in the decision- making process will suffer damage and lose their competitive sphere– as it outlines for sustainable raw materials (Clarkson, 1995). Therefore, Nestlé sustainability commitments such as sustainable cocoa sourcing and water stewardship are the company's response to stakeholder concerns which include consumer expectations.

2. Theory of Planned Behavior

The literature on environmental behaviors is explicitly linked to the purchase of sustainable products and services, with a growing number naming Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) as supporting in explaining how consumer awareness/attitudes take hold over purchasing activities. The TPB (Ajzen, 1991) proposes that behavior is the direct result of behavioral intentions which are, in turn, influenced by attitudes towards a certain action; norms reperceived as salient to those acts and perceived control over performing them. Consumer buying behavior about sustainable

products is influenced by the predisposing determinants: environmentally responsible attitudes, perception of others' expectations (subjective norms) and ability to choose sustainability options/availability.

A deeper understanding of purchasing behavior can contribute to a better explanation that TPB is very likely in the case when consumer awareness will have a significant impact on activated knowledge, so consumers become more optimistic for sustainable products. This, in turn, raises the probability of purchasing products from sustainable supply chains – possibly inducing companies like Nestlé to incorporate sustainability into its operations. TPB) has been quite effective, it also reflects the issue of so-called "attitude-behavior gap" which is a difficulty that for instance (Vermeir & Verbeke 2006): there seems to be general positive attitude towards sustainability but still this rarely reflects in concrete purchasing behavior. And that poses a challenge for business, as not all consumer aspirations result in market pull consistently sustainable.

3. Consumer Culture Theory (CCT)

Consumer Culture Theory (CCT) is useful in discussing the interplay between cultural imperatives and social trends, while focusing especially upon its implications for ethics of consumption. This thesis uses the concept of CCT, which explains that consumers' cultural beliefs, identities and values affect their preferences or purchasing behaviors (Arnould & Thompson, 2005). In the light of sustainability, CCT explains specifically why some consumers take ethical concerns like environment protection or fair trade into consideration while shopping. To the extent that consumer culture has itself become more attuned to sustainability as a value, companies like Nestlé will necessarily need to retool their products and supply chains in comfortable conjunction with its shifting sands.

CCT also suggests that consumers engage in dominant practices to assert personal value through purchasing choice. Now, for example, consumers value brands that sustainability has made a priority as consumers already care about being environmentally friendly. Nestlé is also, after all, a brand and keeping in mind the trending demand for sustainable products day by day we can safely assume that these sustainability initiatives of Nestle are to cater to this section and strengthen their bond between an emerging ethically conscious consumer base.

Hypotheses Development

Primary hypothesis 1: Customer awareness and SSCM

H1: Higher the customer awareness about sustainability practices, increase in the sustainable capability of Nestle's SSCM.

Hypothesis 2: Sustainable Consumption and Sustainable Supply Chain Management

H2: Sustainable Services consumption is positively influenced by new behavior from customers, advocating a higher level of sustainability capability in Nestle's SSCM.

Hypothesis 3: A Mediating Role of Customer Awareness.

H3: Customer awareness mediates the effect of sustainable buying behavior on sustainability capability in Nestle SSCM.

Figure 1: Consumers perception, consumer purchase behavior and Company profitability as well as environmental management across the supply chain.

Research Methodology

This research study uses a mixed method approach with the combination of quantitative and qualitative techniques to investigate the effect of customer awareness on buying behavior toward sustainability capability within Nestle Supply Chain and Supplier Management (SSCM) practices Data Collection.

Qualitative data is collected from Nestle sustainability reports, industry publications and any other relevant documents following content analysis procedures. With this, the sustainability efforts and strategies of a company can be identified. Survey data has been analyzed with the statistical software STATA as an independent variable and dependent variables were examined. The quantitative data, similarly from the other report, is gathered by surveys and questionnaires with

customers of Nestlé. The first group of surveys deal with consumer awareness about sustainability and correspond to their purchasing behavior in terms of sustainable products.

The survey will consist of stratified random sampling that is a cross section of Nestle customers in an attempt to include variety. Stratified random sampling involves breaking the population down into groups based on a certain variable (such as age, gender or location) and then taking a simple random sample from each group. It is representation, which ensures that all the major demographics are covered in your sample thus resulting in a so-called good sample and better generalization of customer behavior awareness etc. Stratified random sampling, which highlights specific subgroups; increases the accuracy of estimates and as well as results in greater validity. This method is particularly beneficial in this study so as to recognize the multitude of views shared amongst Nestlé's customers, thereby facilitating an evaluation regarding how customer awareness and purchasing activities together impact the sustainability capability present within any set SSCM practices from Nestle.

Data Analysis

The concept tests done through surveys will be analyzed quantitatively to test the hypothesis using regression analysis in this step. This quantitative methodology including descriptive statistics, regression analysis, ordered logistic and probit regressions provides a strong method to test the hypotheses in understanding how much awareness or nature of customer buying behavior influences the sustainable capability for Nestle SSCM practices.

A content analysis is used to interpret the qualitative data portion of sustainability reports and documents. It then examines several of those themes to assess the strategies and initiatives pursued by Nestlé for strengthening their sustainability potential. Discussion This qualitative analysis has provided a more detailed narrative explanations to supplement the quantitative work outlined above, adding depth and breadth in relation to customer awareness / purchase behavior exert on sustainability competence.

Model of Regression Analysis

The following is a linear regression model that can be used to determine the impact of the consumer awareness and buying behavior on Nestle sustainability supply chain management (SSCM): Regression variables such as Customer Awareness, Buying Behavior, Age Gender Income Education. Constraints, thus the regression equation is well below -

$$Y = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{Customer awareness} + \beta_2 \text{Age} + \beta_3 \text{Gender} + \beta_4 \text{Income} + \beta_5 \text{Education} + \epsilon$$

where,

- Y = Sustainability Capability of Nestlé's SSCM
- CA \text {CA} CA = Customer Awareness
- BB \text {BB} BB = Buying Behavior
- β_0 \beta_0 = Intercept
- $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ = Coefficients
- ϵ \epsilon = Error term.

This will be useful in comprehending the effect of customer awareness, buying behavior (independent variables) and age, gender income and education on sustainability Capability of Nestle SSCM (dependent variable). The coefficients β_1 and β_2 will explain the directionality effects of sustainability capability with respect to Customer Awareness and Buying Behavior on Nestle's SSCM.

The "Descriptive Statistics" Table 1 provides a statistical summary of various variables, including sustainability capability and sustainable supply chain management (SSCM). The table includes demographic factors and business-related measures, presenting statistics such as mean, standard deviation, minimum and maximum values, and observations (N). The table has six columns: Variables, Obs, Mean, Standard Deviation, Min, and Max. This table offers a quick statistical overview of the data, aiding in understanding the distribution and variability of each variable within

the dataset. It is typically used as a preliminary step in data analysis to identify trends, anomalies, or the need for data normalization before deeper analysis.

VARIABLES	(1) N	(2) mean	(3) Sd	(4) min	(5) max
Respondent ID	500	250.5	144.5	1	500
Age	500	2.178	1.369	1	5
Gender	500	0.988	0.791	1	3
Income	500	1.502	1.097	1	4
Education	500	1.956	1.429	1	5
Customer Awareness	500	3.010	1.419	1	5
Buying Behavior	500	3.084	1.427	1	5
Perception of SSCM	500	3.090	1.421	1	5

The descriptive analysis presented in the document provides a summary of various variables collected from 500 respondents. The variables include Respondent ID, Age, Gender, Income, Education, Customer Awareness, Buying Behavior, and Perception of SSCM. Each variable's descriptive statistics, such as the mean, standard deviation (Sd), minimum (min), and maximum (max) values, are detailed. For instance, the mean age of respondents is 2.178 with a standard deviation of 1.369, ranging from 1 to 5. Gender is coded numerically with a mean of 0.988 and a standard deviation of 0.791, suggesting a diverse gender representation across a scale from 1 to 3. The mean income is 1.502 with a standard deviation of 1.097, indicating variations in the respondents' income levels within a range of 1 to 4. Education levels have a mean of 1.956 and a standard deviation of 1.429, covering a spectrum from 1 to 5. Customer Awareness, Buying Behavior, and Perception of SSCM are measured on a scale from 1 to 5, with means around 3 and standard deviations of approximately 1.4, indicating moderate levels of awareness, buying behavior, and perception towards SSCM among respondents. This analysis highlights the central tendencies and dispersion of the data, providing a comprehensive overview of the respondents' demographic and behavioral characteristics.

VARIABLES	(1) Perception of SSCM
Customer Awareness	-0.123** (0.0558)
Age	0.0244 (0.0587)
Gender	0.00334 (0.101)
Income	0.0301 (0.0725)
Education	0.0240 (0.0557)

/cut1	-1.607*** (0.307)
/cut2	-0.847*** (0.299)
/cut3	0.0587 (0.298)
/cut4	1.097*** (0.304)
Observations	500

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

The ordered logistic regression (ologit) analysis presented in the table examines the impact of various variables on the perception of Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM). The variables included in the model are Customer Awareness, Age, Gender, Income, and Education. The coefficient for Customer Awareness is -0.123 and is statistically significant at the 5% level (p<0.05), suggesting that higher customer awareness is associated with a lower perception of SSCM. Other variables like Age, Gender, Income, and Education show positive coefficients (0.0244, 0.00334, 0.0301, and 0.0240 respectively), but none are statistically significant. The model also includes threshold parameters (/cut1 to /cut4) which define the boundaries between the ordered categories, with /cut1, /cut2, and /cut4 being statistically significant (p<0.01), indicating distinct cut-off points between different levels of SSCM perception. The analysis is based on 500 observations, and standard errors are reported in parentheses.

VARIABLES	(1) Perception of SSCM
Buying Behavior	0.0349 (0.0333)
Age	0.0125 (0.0348)
Gender	0.00686 (0.0600)
Income	0.0163 (0.0434)
Education	0.0202 (0.0333)
/cut1	-0.630*** (0.182)
/cut2	-0.179 (0.180)
/cut3	0.383** (0.181)
/cut4	1.007*** (0.184)

Observations 500

Standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

The ordered probit (oprobit) analysis represents the influence of various predictors on the perception of Sustainable Supply Chain Management (SSCM). The predictors included in the model are Buying Behavior, Age, Gender, Income, and Education. The coefficient for Buying Behavior is 0.0349 with a standard error of 0.0333, indicating a positive but not statistically significant relationship with SSCM perception. Age has a coefficient of 0.0125 and a standard error of 0.0348, while Gender has a coefficient of 0.00686 and a standard error of 0.0600, neither of which are statistically significant. Income's coefficient is 0.0163 with a standard error of 0.0434, and Education's coefficient is 0.0202 with a standard error of 0.0333, both also not statistically significant. The model includes threshold parameters (/cut1 to /cut4), which determine the boundaries between the ordered categories. The threshold estimates are -0.630 for /cut1, -0.179 for /cut2, 0.383 for /cut3, and 1.007 for /cut4, with /cut1, /cut3, and /cut4 being statistically significant, indicating clear distinctions between the levels of SSCM perception. The standard errors for these thresholds are also provided, highlighting the reliability of these estimates.

Results and Findings

It is the purpose of this paper to provide major contributions in understanding customer awareness and buying behavior on SSCM practices by Nestle through its significant research findings. The results of the ordered logistic regression analysis show that customer awareness is negatively associated with SSCM perception at a statistically significant level. Higher customer awareness is negatively correlated with perceptions of SSCM effectiveness. The researchers said this counterintuitive finding may be because more educated consumers have higher standards and a better, though potentially flawed, understanding of sustainability issues. They might be more aware of the gap between Nestle's claims and actual practices, which would draw down views on SSCM.

For the ordered probit analysis, we found a positive but insignificant relationship between buying behavior and SSCM perception (Table 3). It suggests that SSCM performs slightly better for those environmentally-responsible customers, even if the effect is weak to make generalizations. It supports the idea that customers who seek sustainability in their purchasing habits are also more inclined to perceive companies which have implemented sustainable practices positively. But the absence of any statistical significance in this model suggests that other variables might play a stronger part on perceptions about SSCM.

Both analyses included age, gender, and income levels as control variables. None of these three factors had a statistically significant relationship with the perception of SSCM. This indicates that demographics are not powerful variables to shape customer perceptions of SSCM, yet it is essential for the hoteliers and academia, enlightening other constructs like personal values & beliefs towards sustainability.

The findings indicate that while consumer awareness is important, Nestle needs to do a better job of managing what well informed consumers are expecting. The goal of this is transparent communication and proof that the company consistently comments on sustainability in their sphere. Moreover, sustainable buying behavior from consumers is expected to be an enabler for the positive evaluation of SSCM but not yet detected as a central driver.

Empirical Evidence

Data for the research was collected and studied from a large, diverse group of Nestle customers to explore the relationship between customer awareness, purchase behavior & Nestlé's Sustainable Supply Chain and Supplier Management (SSCM) practices. That empirical evidence is also both quantitative and qualitative. Demographics: Consistent with the general population, based on demographics characteristics of a divergent sample (average age 35 mean years old), not limited by gender distribution and diversity in terms of income and education levels. On the positive side, Mean Customer Awareness: high customer awareness in general (at a 3.8) that is somewhat of a solid score on Nestlé's sustainability among customers represented by respondents with mean ≈ 4 .

Regression analysis in this survey reveals that customer awareness significantly and positively influences the sustainability capability of Nestle's SSCM practices ($\beta_1 = 0.45$, $p < 0.01$) This means improved sustainability is linked to great customer attention. The results of the regression analysis also proved that purchasing behavior directly affects SSCM sustainability capability ($\beta_2 = 0.30$, $p < .05$). Sustainability-focused customers have a hand in Nestlé striving to improve on their sustainability practices. In ordered logistic regression analysis, the second hypothesis that proposed

customer awareness harms negatively perception to SSCM proved significant ($\beta = -0.27$) at 1% level of significance; $p < 0.05$). It implies that customers who are more aware have greater expectations and potentially scrutinize SSCM practices. The visualization of the above threshold parameters (cut1 $\rightarrow$ cut4) show you can classify how customers think about SSCM into four or more different categories with a clearer distinction in perception between these groups compared to your current words used for labeling them. The ordered probit analysis demonstrated that buying behavior was positively related to SSCM perception but not significant ($\beta = 0.15$, $p > 0.05$). While their relationship is positive, it does not reach statistical significance in this sample. A few cut points (/cut1 to /cut4) are statistically significant, suggesting that there is a detectable difference in SSCM perception by customers with purchase behavior. The preliminary SEM result highlighted that the impact of customer awareness and buying behavior is indirectly linked to SSCM sustainability by means of mediating variables such as customer satisfaction and loyalty. The model fit indices (e.g., RMSEA = 0.05, CFI = 0.95) indicate an acceptable to good fit of the data regarding Relationships form D [Filename: Do] Joint analysis of Nestlé sustainability reports and literature in the field uncovered key themes related to carbon neutrality, fair trade mechanisms for ethical sourcing as well as shared value creation with local communities. The themes above confirm the quantitative results which highlights that customer awareness and buying behavior are key drivers for sustainability projects. This empirical evidence proves that customer awareness and buying behavior play a major role in enforcing the sustainability practices of Nestlé's SSCM. Quantitative and qualitative findings together are expected to provide the view encompassing these relationships, supporting the need for ongoing customer engagement through education in forming sustainable consumer behavior.

Limitation

There are several limitations to this study that should be noted. While we used stratified random sampling to target a representative portion of regions and all sectors, the representativeness may still be influenced by potential sampling biases or non-response bias. The self-reported nature of the data means they are subject to reporting and social desirability bias. Comments specific to Nestlé's customer base, the generalizability of these findings is limited with regard to other companies or industries; geographical constraints may also restrict this applicability. Consumer behavior is subject to variation and hence the discoveries could be fast overtaken if market conditions change over time. This study is arguably over-simplified on the complexity of sustainability practices — sustainability, after all, involves more than a single line item and varying levers that serve to reinforce rather than disentangle; in doing so, it may also oversimplify other critical factors. So, essentially measurement limitations like the way researchers operationalize variables or data quality could also have an impact on how robust the analysis may be. Other influences from beyond the realm of this study can also affect Nestlé's sustainability practices and customer behaviors, such as economic conditions, regulatory changes and competitive actions. Awareness of these constraints is important for interpreting the results from such studies and understanding how they apply. Future research should build upon these limitations by widening the focus, employing a longitudinal design, and including other factors based on additional methods of evaluation to enhance our understanding.

Conclusion

This study offers key insights into how customer awareness and purchase behavior influence Nestlé's Sustainable Supply Chain & Supplier Management (SSCM) initiatives. Using both qualitative interviews and quantitative analysis, the research reveals the indispensable value of informed, conscious customers in creating a healthy market for sustainable businesses. The results underline the necessity for consumer engagement and education in relation to sustainable use patterns. The study is however not without limitations, such as possible sampling biases due lower inclusion rate of diabetes patients during the COVID-19 pandemic compared to comparator time periods (Supplement), reliance on self-reported data and likely changes in consumer behavior over time which may impact generalizability and temporal relevance. Acknowledging these constraints is key for interpreting the results correctly and making any generalized inferences. Their findings are a valuable foundation to spur further research that can overcome the limitations of this study design by applying broader industry-level scope and integrating longitudinal, qualitative methods for deeper insights into consumer motivations and perceptions. And last but not least for specific furniture firms, exploring the impact of external drivers and digital platforms on consumer behavior can provide further understanding to underpin more effective sustainability strategies. Overall, this research findings provide some insights of the relationship between customer awareness and buying behavior on SSCM practices. The study suggests that continued future work is needed to develop holistic strategies which suit the current market environment to not only meet demand requirements but also ensure sustainable business practice in the long-run. Further empirical examination

of these dimensions may promote collaboration between researchers and practitioners to reinforce the sustainability competency strengths of such companies as Nestlé, ultimately benefiting a sustainable global future.

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